

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

PHYLOGENETIC ANALYSIS OF NODULE BACTERIA *ESPARSETA ONOBRYCHIS SP.*, USING 16S rDNA

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Abstract

Rhizobia were isolated from the root nodules of perennial plant *Esparseta Onobrychis sp.*, from Desert of Central Asia. The phylogeny of the isolates was investigated using 16S rDNA. The phylogenetic tree of the 16S rDNA showed that many of the isolates belonged to *Rhizobium sp.*, *Sinorhizobium sp.*, *Pantoea agglomerans*, and to *Paenibacillus polymyxa* strain. The acetylene reduction activity was higher for the many isolates inoculated with host plants in micro vegetation experiments. The plasmid profile showed to the *Rhizobial* isolates has some many big plasmids, analogical to *Sinorhizobium meliloti* 41AK631. When the plant was re-inoculated with new nodule bacteria, a high activity of reducing acetylene per plant was observed, and the effective plant growth was higher of the first once. Based on these data, we assume that an effective rhizobia inoculant has been identified for the plant *Esparseta Onobrychis sp.*

Keywords: Nitrogen fixation; 16S rDNA: plant *Esparseta Onobrychis sp.*, *Sym plasmids*

INTRODUCTION. The perennial plant *Esparseta Onobrychis sp.*, belonging to the legume family, is characterized by a powerful development of the root system. Their shoots are 75-100 cm high and above. In Central Asia, they are distributed mainly in desert and arid zones. Due to their ability to form nodules on the roots and high nitrogen-fixing ability, they are less demanding of moisture than other legumes; they are valuable forage plants, rich in protein and other nutrients, resistant to high drought resistance and sufficient winter hardiness [1].

Bacteria of the genus *Esparseta Onobrychis sp.*, with wide host specificity, are found in the Arctic and subarctic regions. Prevost and all showed that in legumes growing in the northern regions, these bacteria enter into symbiosis and form nodules, and nodule-forming genes (Nods) were characterized as the first step towards changing the specificity of the nodule host [3].

The genetic diversity of rhizobium isolates isolated from wild legume species *Esparseta Onobrychis sp.*, originating from different geographical locations, was evaluated using the analysis of 16S rRNA gene polymorphism at the restriction site (MRSP) and PCR DNA fingerprinting with repeated sequences (REP-PCR) [4]. From the REP-PCR data, the authors identified only three examples in which rhizobia of the same plant species appeared to be closely related (two strains of *Astragalus sinicus*, Two strains of *Onobrychis vicifolia*, and three strains of *Astragalus cicer*. These results are consistent with previous classifications in other publications on serology, numerical taxonomy, and cross-infection experiments involving rhizobia from *Astragalus*, *Oxytropis*, and *Onobrychis spp.* They were grouped regardless of their plant origin [4].

The aim of the work was to study the genetic diversity and phylogeny of nodule bacteria of wild legume species from the arid zones of Central Asia and to develop approaches to using the biological potential of these bacteria.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Pink nodules were collected from the root of a plant species *Esparseta Onobrychis*. The nodules were sterilized in ethyl alcohol at 96°C for 5 minutes. Then it was washed several times with bi-distilled water, and placed in an Eppendorf tube and blown with a sterile glass wand until a homogeneous mass was obtained, bi-distilled water containing 10% sucrose was added, the liquid part was diluted several times and grown on a solid agarized dish with a medium for nodule bacteria, as described in the article [5]. Bacterial colonies appeared within three days. Bacteriologically pure nodule bacteria were isolated from single grown colonies.

Microvegetation experiments. For microvegetation experiments *Esparseta Onobrychis sp.*, seeds were treated by concentrated sulphuric acid during 6-7 minutes, then after their numerous washing by sterile water the treated seeds were put on sterile Petri dishes and were incubated in thermostat at 30°C temperature for 1-2 days. After before their germination, were collected the same size (length of seedlings). The germinated seeds further were introduced into tubes with volume 60 ml with sterile vermiculite (3:1), height of which was 8 cm, containing nutritive medium for plants, as written in S. Fedorov et all, [6].

Determination of nitrogen-fixing activit. Nitrogen-fixing activity was assessed using the acetylene reductase activity (APA) assay described by Hardy [7]. Plant samples (with root nodules) were washed with sterile water and placed in agronomic tubes with a capacity of 60 ml, equipped with sealed rubber stoppers. Acetylene (10% by volume) was injected and the tubes were incubated at 30°C for 24 hours. The data obtained was average for three repetitions. Acetylene-free samples were used as a control. The quantitative assessment of ethylene gas formed in the samples was carried out on a gas chromatograph (LHM-80). Acetylene reeducates activity in plants was expressed in nmols of C₂H₄ per tube per hour.

CTAB is the extraction of genomic DNA. Bacterial nodule cells were grown to a logarithmic phase,

and genomic DNA was isolated from these cells, as indicated in Professor Sharon Long's laboratory protocol manual. With some modifications [8], as well as according to the method of Dr. J.Marmura [8].

PCR amplification of the 16S rRNA gene. The 16S rDNA genes from nodule bacteria were amplified using universal primers 1070f (59-ACGGGCGGTGTGTAC-39) and 1392r (59-CGCCCGCCGCGCCCCGCGCCCCCGCCCCCGCCCCCGCGGTGTGTAC-39), as described in M.J.Ferris et al., 1996 [9].

Phylogenetic analysis. The complete sequences of 16S rDNA genes with a length of 300-354 bp were compared with the sequences available in the GenBank database using the standard BLASTn basic local alignment search tool [10] at the National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) (<http://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Blast.cgi>). Dendrograms connecting neighbors were constructed from aligned sequences [11] using the MEGA software version 4.0.2 [12]. The reliability of the obtained trees was evaluated using 1000 repeated bootstrap samples.

RESULTS. The nodules were collected from plants that had grown to one meter and placed in an agar medium to maintain humidity. The isolation of bacteria is described in the section materials and methods. Microscopic studies of some bacterial cells of the selected strains showed that the studied cells were represented by typical movable rods. The growth rate of the isolated nodule bacteria strains depends on the cultivation conditions and is one of the most important taxonomic features. At the same time, a well-formed colony of fast-growing bacteria can be obtained after 3-4 days of

growth, and for slow-growing ones - after 7-10 days. In a medium containing agar-agar, isolates of nodule bacteria formed colorless, transparent, mucous colonies. This type of colony of isolates was typical for S-forms of bacteria

We have tested the resistance of these bacteria to antibiotics. The table shows the data.

There were used Ampicillin (100 µg/ml), Vancomycin (100 µg/ml), Rifampicin (100 µg/ml), Neomycin (50, 100 µg/ml), Kanamycin (100 µg/ml), Streptomycin (100, 200 µg/ml), Chloramphenicol (50, 100 µg/ml), which had been added into agarized TY medium. The bacterial growth on these antibiotic-containing TY medium was checked during 3 days at 30°C in thermostat.

For all types of rhizobia, a high level of stamp diversity is observed in natural populations, in particular, in the composition of plasmids. The genes responsible for the formation of an effective symbiosis with a legume plant are localized in rhizobia mainly on a high-molecular (up to 1000 microns) "symbiotic" plasmid. In addition to Sym, plasmids in bacterial cells contain up to nine plasmids of different molecular weights (400, 500 and 600 microns), which are called cryptic. However, the functional role of these plasmids is unclear. For some strains of rhizobia, it has been shown that the presence of cryptic plasmids can affect the viability of bacteria or determine their adaptive abilities (Rastogi V. K. et al., 1992; Djordjevic et al., 1982). [13, 14]. However, the survival of strains in the soil often depends on their resistance to stress factors (temperature, salt tolerance, etc.). In addition, the role of host plants as the main ecological selective factor affecting the number and structure of populations of soil rhizobia is widely discussed.

Table.1.

Antibiotic resistance isolates Rhizobium Onobrychis transcaucasica

	<i>Amp</i> 100	<i>Van</i> 100	<i>Rif</i> 100	<i>Nm</i> 50	<i>Nm</i> 100	<i>Km</i> 25	<i>Km</i> 100	<i>Str</i> 100	<i>Str</i> 200	<i>Cm</i> 30	<i>Cm</i> 50	<i>Cm</i> 100
<i>T-102</i>	+	+	+			-	+	-			+	+
<i>T-103</i>	+	+	+			-	-				+	+
<i>T-111</i>	+	+	+			-	+	-	+	+	+	+
<i>T-115</i>	+	+	+	+		-	+	-	+	+	+	+
<i>T-117</i>	+	+	+	+		-	-				+	+
<i>T-118</i>	+	+	+			-	-				+	+
<i>T-121</i>	-	+	+	+		-	+	-	+		+	+
<i>T-122</i>	+	+	+			-	-	+			+	+
<i>T-123</i>	+	+	+	+		-	-				+	+
<i>T-130</i>	+	+	+			-	-	+	+		+	+
<i>T-136</i>	+	+	+			-	-	+	+		+	+
<i>T-139</i>	+	+	+			-	-	+			+	+
<i>T-140</i>	+	+	+	+		-	+	-	+		+	+
<i>CH-7</i>	+	+	+	+		-	-	+	+		+	+

Pic. 2, Eckhardt-type gel electrophoresis showing plasmid profiles of isolated bacteria that had the Sym plasmids.

Lanes: 1-4, 7-9 *Rhizobium Onobrychis* sp., lines 5-6 *Paenibacillus polymyxa*., line 10 *Sinorhizobium meliloti* 41AK631. The bands corresponding to plasmids *Rhizobium*

The plasmid profile has executed according to Eckhardt's method revealed that we did not find plasmids in the genome of *Paenibacillus polymyxa*. line 4-5, Compared to the control line 10. (plasmid *Sinorhizobium meliloti* 41AK631). In line 1,2,3,4, and 7,8,9 where were *Rhizobium Onobrychis* were high molecular plasmids with size 1800 bp. This results indicates that the main symbiotic nitrogen fixation genes are integrated in these Sym plasmids [15].

Microvegetation and vegetation experiments.

The seeds for experiments on growing microvegetations were treated with concentrated sulfuric acid for 5 minutes, followed by repeated rinsing with sterile water. The treated seeds were placed in sterile Petri dishes containing 1% agar and incubated in a thermostat at 30°C for 1-2 days. The germinated seeds were placed in glass tubes with a volume of 60 ml, and 8 ml of this medium were added. as written in the Materials and methods section, Fedorov S.N. et al., 1983. [6]. The plants were inoculated with a bacterial suspension in the amount of 10^9 cells/ml and grown in sterile greenhouse conditions for 45 days. Each vaccination option has 10 repetitions of 1 plan in one repeat. The nitrogen-fixing activity of nodule bacteria was determined by the activity of acetylene reductase on an LHM chromatograph. These data for *Onobrychis transcaucasica* plants ranged from 28 to 63 nmol C_2H_4 /hour/tube, and for *Onobrychis chorassanica* from 29 to 51 nmol C_2H_4 /hour/tube [7].

CTAB genomic DNA extraction. We used the method Dr. J.Marmur with some modification. This method has been described for the isolation of DNA from micro-organisms. The isolated DNA from micro-organisms is biologically active, highly polymerized preparations relatively free from protein and RNA. The modifications methods of cell disruption and DNA isolation have been described and compared with isolated DNA from other cultures microorganisms.

PCR amplification of the 16S rDNA gene. For the amplification 16s rDNA region genome we used several universal primers which used from many scientists to amplify the 16s rRNA region of the genome, but none of these primers could synthesize the ribosomal

region, only those primers used by Dr. M.J.Ferris were fully amplified 16s rRNA region of the genome. The nucleotide sequence of this site was determined from the databank NCBI that these bacteria belong to nitrogen-fixing bacteria, and in addition to it, they are very close relatives. The 16S rRNA gene from nodule bacteria of *Onobrychis transcaucasica* and *Onobrychis chorassanica* was amplified using universal primers 1070f and 1392r as written in the article M.J.Ferris et al., 1996 [9].

Phylogenetic analysis of the 16S rRNA gene of nodule bacteria strains. The taxonomy of bacterial isolates isolated from the nodules of *Onobrychis transcaucasica* and *Onobrychis chorassanica* plants was studied using the 16S rDNA gene method. The nucleotide sequence of the 16S rDNA gene of the site made it possible to identify the specific affiliation of bacteria to the genus, and for some bacteria, down to the species. The results of a comparative BLAST analysis of the nucleotide sequence of the conserved region of the 16S rRNA gene of bacteria 4-isolates from *Onobrychis transcaucasica* were 99% identical to the genes of *Rhizobium etli* strain SEMIA 284 16S ([AY904730.1](#)) Interestingly, the nucleotide sequences of bacteria 9-isolates from *Onobrychis transcaucasica* also have 96-98% identity with the genes of *Sinorhizobium meliloti* CCNWYC140 ([EU849576.1](#)), *Sinorhizobium meliloti* ([AB535707.1](#)), *Sinorhizobium fredii* CCBAU 10078 ([GU552900.1](#)), *Mesorhizobium mediterraneum* Zw-2-1 ([GU201845.1](#)), *Mesorhizobium obiense* Zw-1 ([GU201844.1](#)), *Bradyrhizobium japonicum* PRY65 ([AF239848.2](#)) bacteria. The conservative region of 16S rRNA gene of OT114, OT124, OT148 bacteria coincides by 98-99% with genes of *Pantoea agglomerans* GS2 ([GQ374474.1](#)), *Enterobacter cloacae* IHB B 1374 ([GU186117.1](#)) and *Pantoea agglomerans* MKPTK-4 bacteria ([GQ499274.1](#)) accordingly, and *Paenibacillus polymyxa* strain GBR-477 ([AY359625.1](#)) and ([AY359620.1](#)), respectively.

Similar results were obtained for nodule bacteria from *Onobrychis chorassanica*. Analysis of the 16S rRNA genes of the nodule bacterium *Onobrychis cho-*

rassanica showed that the nucleotide sequence of bacteria OC104, OC107, OC109, and OC111 coincides by 98-99% with the genes of *Rhizobium etli* strain SEMIA 284 16S (AY904730.1)

Moreover, 16S rRNA genes of OC104, OC107, OC109 bacteria by 97-99% were homologous with genes of several bacteria species such as *Sinorhizobium meliloti* CCNWX C140 (EU849576.1), *Sinorhizobium meliloti* YcS2 (AB535707.1), *Sinorhizobium fredii* CCBAU 10078 (GU552900.1), *Mesorhizobium tianshanense* (FM203306.1), *Mesorhizobium amorphae* CCNWYC131 (EU849577.1) and *Bradyrhizobium japonicum* PRY62 bacteria (AF239847.2). The bacterium OC112 is 99% identical by with nucleotide sequences of 16S rRNA gene of *Burkholderia caryophylli* WAB1944 (AM184283.1), the genes of OC106 coincides by 97% with genes of *Pantoea agglomerans*

HXJ (HM016799.1), genes of OC138 by 98% coincides with genes of *Enterobacter* sp. RF-100 (GQ205104.1) and genes of OC113 bacteria by 97% are identical with genes of *Enterobacter* sp. B-13M3 (AJ874743.1).

When studying the phylogenetic tree based on the nucleotide sequences of 16S RNA, various bacteria were found that studied 9 isolates of *Onobrychis transcaucasica* belonging to the class of alpha-proteobacteria (Figure 4a), but the bacteria OT114, OT124, OT148 were classified as gammaproteobacteria. The phylogenetically ancient nodule bacterium *Onobrychis chorassanica*, unlike the bacterium *Onobrychis transcaucasica*, has three clusters. The bacteria included in the 1st cluster were alpha-proteobacteria, the 2nd cluster was beta-proteobacteria, the bacteria of the 3rd cluster belonged to the class of gammaproteobacteria, in particular to the genera *Enterobacter* and *Pantoea* (Fig.4)

Figure 4. Phylogenetic tree based on the 16S rDNA gene strains of nodule bacteria *Onobrychis chorassanica*: a- Alphaproteobacteria; b- Betaproteobacteria; c- Gammaproteobacteria. The branching pattern was produced by the neighbour-joining method. The GenBank accession numbers for the sequences used are indicated in parentheses. Symbionts of *Onobrychis chorassanica* are shown in bold type.

DISCUSSION. The success of the process of nodulation and nitrogen fixation depends on the successful survival ability, competitiveness, and efficiency of the rhizobial strains involved. Redmond et al. 1986; Lerouge et al. 1990; Polonenko et al. 1993; Prevost et al. 2003, in scientific investigations has been shown in within the soil, various factors like type and variety of host and bacterial strains, soil physical and chemical properties, temperature, light, plays and important role

in interaction with other rhizospheric microorganisms [18, 19, 20, 21]. One way to achieve successful symbiosis and nitrogen fixation is to provide optimum conditions to rhizobia inoculants which are not possible under field conditions.

It was previously shown that edaphic factors and prevailing environmental conditions determine the distribution of the rhizobia population. For example, soil pH and P, temperature, salinity and moisture content

strongly influence the diversity of rhizobia strains in various agro ecological regions [22, 23, and 24].

However, the sufficiency of the symbiosis to meet plant N requirements was not reported. Prevost D, Bordeleau L.M and Antoun H, (1987a), Prevost, Bordeleau, Caudry-Reznick, Schulman, and Antoun (1987b), Prévost et al. (2003) showed enhanced growth of arctic rhizobium at 5°C, as well as effective nodulation in sainfoin. [25, 26, 27, 28].

D.K.Jain, D.Prévost, L.M.Bordeleau. (1990) also used arctic rhizobium along with mutagenesis and documented improved N_2 fixation with selected strains, indicative that optimization of the inoculant for sainfoin is possible and deserves further attention [29].

Laguerre et al. 1997; Prevost and Bromfield 2001; Prevost et al. 2003, in own scientific works have written that the bacteroids observed within the *Astragalus* nodules were clearly expressing the nifH protein of nitrogenase, thus reinforcing the strong likelihood that the plants were fixing N_2 at the time that they were harvested [4]. Although the exact nature of the *Astragalus* symbionts is so far unknown, cold-adapted *Mesorhizobium* strains were the principal symbionts isolated from *A. arcticus* and from species of the closely related genus *Oxytropis* in Canada [30].

Conclusions

In conclusion of our discussion, those nodule bacteria in associations enter into nitrogen-fixing symbiosis with plant hosts. Based on the data obtained, in the discussion we showed several scientific works of scientists who studied the nitrogen fixation properties of nodule bacteria in cold conditions. In the Arid zones there are many stress factors, such as water stress, temperature, pH and others, and in these conditions, the struggle for the survival of microorganisms occurs due to their activity. Microorganisms are attached not only to root plants, but also to nodule of plants themselves.

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